

AN INVESTIGATION OF EXPERIENCED PERSON IN HAND LAY-UP FABRICATION METHOD - CONVERTING TACIT KNOWLEDGE TO EXPLICIT IN THE FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS MOLDING-

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ABSTRACT

Hand lay-up fabrication is a form of craftsmanship and an implicit skill supported by individual sense, and subjective implicit values deep-rooted in expertise and judgment by touch and from appearance based on “instinct” and “know-how” skills inherited from past generations for the evaluation of thickness and impregnation, removal of voids, etc. Typically, more than 20 years of experience is required for a person to become a skilled craftsman in hand lay-up fabrication. Challenges the need to be addressed are how to pass their skills onto future generations, foster artisans, and construct a sustainable manufacturing process. In this study, the authors thus investigated the relation between the pressure force applied by the operator when using a roller for fabrication work and the degree of proficiency.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hand lay-up (HLU) fabrication has been used for forming composite materials since ancient times. The very primitive method is possible as long as the mold, skills, and materials are available. Because the mold is inexpensive and facility costs are also low, it offers the advantage of being able to deal flexibly with changes in production quality, size, and shape. Although it must depend on human strength, its high level of freedom attracts wide interest in areas related to the production of prototypes and small lot production of diverse products such as automobile parts and aerospace materials. On the other hand, because it needs to rely on humans, it has shortcomings such as inconsistency in quality according to the individual performing it, difference in quality between parts that are easy to fabricate and those that are not, and proneness to defects such as air bubbles. Accordingly, highly specialized control technique and tradition of skills are required to ensure the consistent stability of product quality.

Generally, it is thought that the characteristics of the composite material will usually become the same regardless of which forming method is used as long as the reinforced substrate, reinforcement morphology, matrix resin, and volume content of reinforcing material are the same; however, it has been demonstrated that the degree of proficiency of the HLU method has a huge influence on the dimensional stability and mechanical characteristics of the composite material ^[1,2,3,4 and 5].

This means that there exists implicit knowledge that strongly depends on experience and instinct cultivated over a long time with regard to roller operations and evaluation method. It is crucial to identify the effects of the implicit knowledge on roller operations. In the small-lot production of diverse products, the shape and size of products vary extensively, and there is a need to deal with difficult-to-eliminate air bubbles generated due to resin fluctuations (eg, lot, viscosity) and adjustments of roller operations based on experience accumulated over a long period of time. With the slow progress of forming using robots, inevitably human strength must still be depended upon.

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) made of fibers and resins, are basically formed by impregnating fibers with resin, i.e., replacing the air contained in fibers with resin. With the HLU technique, rollers are used to impregnate reinforced fibers with resin. Consequently, the impregnation method is expected to contribute to changes in the properties of the interface formed. However, it is thought that there exists implicit knowledge that strongly depends on long years of experience and instinct with regard to roller operations and evaluation method, and there is a need to clarify the effects of this knowledge on roller operations.

This study aimed to identify the implicit knowledge possessed by experienced craftsmen specializing in making bathtubs using the HLU technique by comparing the work process between such experts and non-experts whose working time and pressure force applied in the use of finishing rollers differ conspicuously according to expertise.

2 Methodology

2.1 Subjects

The subjects were four craftsmen consisting of an expert in HLU with 27 years of experience, and craftsmen with experience of 13 years, 3 years, and 0.5 years, respectively. Table 1 shows the biological data of the subjects.

Subject Person	Age	years of experience (year)	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Dominant-Hand
Expert	50	27	171	52	Right
Intermediate-1	35	13	179	66	Right
Intermediate-2	31	3	164	52	Right
Non-expert	31	0.5	182	77	Right

Table 1: Biological data of subjects.

2.2 Experimental Protocol

The subjects carried out FRP forming by HLU on the measuring device (Figure 1). The roller used in this study was that used in normal work. Attached with 3mm hog bristles throughout the whole circumference, the roller measured 14 mm in diameter and 70 mm in width (Figure 2). Video was taken using one video camera. Figure 1 shows the measurements using a reaction force measuring device. As for the coordinates, the front-back direction in respect to the subject was taken to be the x axis, the left-right direction the y axis, and the up-down direction the z axis. Without specifying the roller work time, the subjects were asked to carry out finishing work using the roller until they were satisfied.

The requirements of the finishing roller work were the elimination of voids inside the FRP laminated layers and smoothness of the finished surface. Finishing is an important step in HLU fabrication and the step where difference in the level of experience appears most conspicuously. The

unsaturated polyester resin used in this study changes to gel in 30 minutes because it is a photocurable resin, which means that the work time is restricted.

Figure 1: Measurement environment of this study.

Figure 2 Defoaming roller.

Figure 3 Photo of reaction force measurement (left: x-direction, right: y-direction).

2.3 Materials

Glass fiber chopped strand mat (450g/m²) was used as the reinforced substrate. For the matrix, unsaturated polyester resin made with isophthalic acid was used. A curing agent (MEKPO) was added to the resin at a ratio of 100:1.0. Three glass fiber chopped strand mats were laminated in the forming work. The size of the fabricated FRP sheet was horizontally 300 mm and vertically 200 mm (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Thickness measurement range.

2.4 Measurement of dimensional stability

To compare the dimensional stability of the obtained samples, the thickness of the FRP sheets was measured every 20 mm using a micrometer (Figure 4).

2.5 Measurement of reaction force

To measure the reaction force imposed by the finishing roller on the laminated layers using the HLU method, the reaction force measuring device was used (TF-3040-A, 400 mm × 300 mm, Tec-Gihan) (Figure 5). At a sampling frequency of 100 Hz, the reaction force of all operations from start to end was measured. At the same time, the trajectory of the x-y plane was also measured. The center of gravity of the reaction force is shown for the trajectory. The origin means the center of the reaction force measuring device.

Figure 5: Reaction force measuring device.

3 RESULTS AND CONSIDERATION

3.1 Dimensional stability

Figure 6 shows the distribution of the thickness of the fabricated FRP sheet. The FRP sheet fabricated by the expert had stable thickness in both the X and Y directions, whereas it should be especially noted that the thickness of the FRP sheets fabricated by the non-experts was conspicuously inconsistent at the turning points of the stroke. (The edge of the flat FRP sheet is thin.) Figure 7 compares the average thickness of the FRP sheets fabricated by each subject. It can be clearly seen that the thickness of the sheet fabricated by the expert is stable around 2.1mm in both the x and y directions. Inconsistency in the thickness was also small and the finished surface was smooth. On the other hand, the finished surface by the non-experts appears rough and undulated even to the naked eye, and the inconsistency of the thickness is large. The average thickness and number of years of experience were found to be closely correlated among the three subjects excluding the subject with experience of 0.5 years (simple correlation coefficient: 0.97).

Figure 6: Comparison of dimensional stability.

Figure 7: Relation between average thickness and years of experience.

These results suggest that how the roller is used clearly affects the thickness of the planar, elevation, and R convex sections, in other words the stability of the shape. In addition, it is evident that how the roller is used is closely related to operations that define “career,” as shown in Figure 7.

3.2 Compressive Pressure of Roller

The effects of years of experience on compressive pressure of roller were investigated. Figure 8 and 9 show the trajectory of roller.

Figure 8: Comparison of trajectory on x-y plane (x-direction)

Figure 9: Comparison of trajectory on x-y plane (y-direction)

Figure 10 and 11 show the relation between the number of roller and years of experience. In addition, a strong correlation was found between career and the number of roller (coefficient of correlation: 0.95(x-direction), 0.95(y-direction)) except Non expert.

Figure 10: Relation between the number of roller and years of experience (x-direction).

Figure 11: Relation between the number of roller and years of experience (y-direction)

Figure 12 shows the relationship between force of z-axis (compressive pressure of roller) and x-direction.

Figure 12: Comparison of compressive pressure at x-direction.

Figure 13 shows the relation between maximum compressive and pressure years of experience (x-direction). In addition, a strong correlation was found between career and the number of roller (coefficient of correlation: 0.84) except Non expert.

Figure 13: Relation between maximum compressive pressure and years of experience (x-direction).

Figure 14 shows the relation between compressive pressure and y-direction. Figure 15 shows the relation between maximum compressive and pressure years of experience (y-direction). In addition, a strong correlation was found between career and the number of roller (coefficient of correlation: 0.82) except Non expert.

Figure 14: Comparison of compressive pressure at y-direction.

Figure 15: Relation between maximum compressive pressure and years of experience (y-direction).

4 CONCLUSIONS

The findings suggest a close relationship between how the roller is used (e.g., direction, frequency, and load), which is a measure of career, and mechanical property. Characteristics of the expert can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Compressive pressure of roller is evenly distributed. Then the coefficient of variation of the thickness and mechanical strength is estimated to be small.
- 2) Sample thickness that expert finished is uniform; this has been suggested to be responsible for the mechanical properties improved.

Furthermore, it was found that the above four points can be incorporated into the educational tools of non-experts and intermediates, sharply reducing the skill acquirement time. The inclusion has also increased the fun and joy of skill acquirement among them.

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